

ENHANCING LITHIUM-ION-BATTERY PERFORMANCE: METAL-ORGANIC-FRAMEWORKS INTEGRATED SEPARATORS TO IMPROVE THE CYCLE LIFE

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Motivation:

- Increasing demand for efficient energy storage due to:
 - Growing electric mobility and smart devices
 - Rising environmental concerns and push towards sustainable energy solutions.
- Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are currently the most advanced commercial energy storage system.

Challenges:

- Gas formation during charge/discharge cycles:
 - Liquid Electrolyte decomposition (formation of CO, CO₂, H₂, O₂ and RH)
 - Leads to swelling, capacity loss and cell degradation.

Research Approach:

- Functionalization of separators with **Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs)**
 - MOFs are known to have excellent gas-absorption qualities due to their high porosity.
 - The MOFs **Zr-MOF-808** and **Ni-MOF-74** are both chemically stable in the electrolyte.
- Integrate the MOF-samples into various separator materials:
 - Polymer (PVDF-HFP), Celgard Polypropylen (PP), Glass fiber (GF)**
- Increase cycle stability and lifetime of cells by scavenging gases.

Solvothermal Synthesis of Zr-MOF-808 and Ni-MOF-74

Preparation of MOF-integrated Separators

PVDF-HFP 5 w% MOF mixture poured in a cast and cut out into coin cell size separators

Celgard PP 3501 separators coated with 10 w% MOF/PVDF mixture using a doctor blade.

Glass fiber separators coated with the 10w% MOF/PVDF mixture by drop coating.

Electrochemical measurements

Conclusions:

- Successful MOF-synthesis with high crystallinity and porosity confirmed by XRD and SEM analysis
- The GCD testing with lab made NMC622 cathode powder coated electrodes, Li-anode and 1 M LiPF₆ in EC/DMC (50/50) (v/v) electrolyte coin cells showed an improved longcycle stability (ZrMOF-808 95%, Ni-MOF-74 87%, without MOF 12% after 50 cycles)
- The EIS-measurements showed a reduction of the resistances inside of the cell due to the MOF-integration (~50% reduction for Zr-MOF-808 and ~40% for Ni-MOF-74)
- Testing will be continued with the coated commercial separators
- Further tests to analyze the gas adsorption will be carried out

